

AIOT APPLICATION WITH EDGE IMPULSE PLATFORM FOR A TRANSLATOR FROM LIBRAS TO PORTUGUESE LANGUAGE

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Summary- According to IBGE, of the 2.3 million Brazilians with hearing impairment, around 65% know and use the LIBRAS sign language to communicate. There are programs that translate from Portuguese to LIBRAS, but not the other way around. Therefore, in this work an application was developed to identify the signals and translate them into Portuguese, using neural network techniques and with promising initial results.

Key words: AIoT; Edge Impulse; Hearing deficiency; LIBRAS.

INTRODUCTION

Like all scientific areas, Engineering also bases its innovations and research on scenarios capable of improving and/or facilitating the population's accessibility to resources they lack, whether due to physical, social or political disabilities. Bearing in mind that, according to the 2022 demographic census of the Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics (IBGE), it was found that more than 1% of Brazilians, around 2.3 million people, have some type of hearing impairment, a percentage that is growing the older the sample, with 2.9% over 18 and 4.3% over 60 [1].

Still according to the research, the knowledge and use of the Brazilian Sign Language, it was found that among those who had the disability, 61.3% practiced such communication, and when adding to the non-disabled, there are just over 2 million users in the country, being the second most used language in Brazil.

Figure 1 – VLibra [1].

Even so, these numbers represent a low rate in relation to the deaf community. There are applications that seek to collaborate in communication, for example VLibra [2] and HandTalk [3] shown in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2, respectively. In them, the translation is done in a single path from the Portuguese language, whether written or spoken, to a digital drawing with movements representing the translated signs. However, there is a gap for the reverse action, LIBRAS for Portuguese, which would greatly facilitate communication between people with hearing impairment and those without the disability.

Figure 2 – HandTalk [2].

Therefore, this article proposes the development of an application to translate from LIBRAS into Portuguese. As this is a problem with countless reading possibilities for the same signage, the proposal was to use Artificial Intelligence techniques using the Edge Impulse platform [4] and data collected in a database available on the Kaggle platform [5].

The hardware used with the camera to verify the gesture was based on the Arduino BLE33 Sense microcontroller, and the tests were carried out using a Samsung A50 model Smartphone with Android 13 version, as both are capable of receiving the application/digital communication, bringing the idea of Internet of Things (IoT) for the project, coming together in an AIoT (fusion of AI and IoT) experience.

Thus, the objective was to create an easy-to-use tool, with the ability to translate the LIBRAS alphabet into Portuguese from a visualized image.

The choice of alphabet, shown in Fig.3, comes from the way in which LIBRAS communication occurs, which is structured in words produced in continuous movement, and thus requiring video capture and database. In the case of the alphabet, except for the letters J and H, these are static hand positions, which allows for less storage space when working with images.

Figure 3 – Representation of the alphabet in LIBRAS [9].

DEVELOPMENT

The hardware used was based on the Arduino BLE33 Sense microcontroller for dealing with the camera and serial interface for viewing the initial results. The board shown in Fig. 4, known as Arduino Nano 33 IoT, has WiFi and Bluetooth modules for connecting to a network, facilitating low-cost communication, and also has other sensor and actuator resources for various applications [8].

The development of the application for translating LIBRAS into Portuguese was carried out on the Edge Impulse platform, a cloud environment that quickly enables the construction of AI applications, using Machine Learning techniques to train Neural Network models, seeking better accuracy in results [4].

To collect images, we used the data available on the Kaggle platform [5], which already provides separate data for training and testing, which greatly facilitates the data insertion stage in Edge Impulse.

Figure 4 – Arduino Nano 33 IoT [6].

Edge Impulse, as a cloud-resident platform, provides a neural network modeling environment, with various algorithm models and the processing of AI models being carried out by CPUs or GPUs, without the need for high investments in their own computing systems.

The trained and tested model can be embedded in hardware with low energy consumption and even reduced computational power and this technique known as TinyML, makes it possible to take Artificial Intelligence to the edge, reducing the latency of communication networks and generating optimized and integrated applications to users' needs.

TinyML in embedded systems allows the development of IoT applications integrated with Artificial Intelligence as a solution with low energy consumption, such as anomaly detection, object detection, image detection, activity recognition, among others [9][10][11].

The development of the project began with creation on the Edge Impulse online platform, using the free version. For image classification, around 1650 images were added for training each letter, where the machine receives pixel information to learn their relationships and interactions, and 500 images for testing each of them, which were used from the database data made available by the Kaggle platform

[6], containing the letters A, B, C, D, E, F, G, I, L, M, N, O, P, Q, R, S, T, U, V, W and Y.
 The development of the LIBRAS alphabet letter image classification model is shown in Fig. 5.

Figure 5 – ML on Edge Impulse [4].

After developing the model and analyzing the accuracy results, for real user testing, the system was generated in C language and embedded in two different hardware, one being the Arduino Nano 33 BLE Sense as shown in Fig. 6 and the other a smartphone.

Figure 6 – Libra translator embedded on the Arduino IDE platform.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

With a set of 33 thousand images divided into 75% for training the neural network and 25% for testing the proposed model, the training accuracy was 90.65% with a loss of 0.06, with a more accurate description of each term shown in Fig. 7, where the first column defines the letter, the second the accuracy (trend), the third the precision (repeatability) and the last the recall (ratio between the predicted true positives and what was actually marked).

	F1-SCORE	PRECISION	RECALL
A	0.94	0.98	0.91
B	0.92	0.97	0.95
C	0.93	0.97	0.95
D	0.92	0.93	0.94
E	0.92	0.97	0.97
F	0.94	0.92	1.00
G	0.94	0.92	0.97
I	0.93	0.96	0.95
L	0.95	0.95	0.96
M	0.89	0.89	0.96
N	0.91	0.95	0.87
O	0.92	0.95	0.95
P	1.00	0.99	1.00
Q	0.98	0.96	0.95
R	0.92	0.89	0.94
S	0.96	0.94	0.95
T	0.92	0.99	0.95
U	0.92	1.00	0.71
V	0.89	1.00	0.99
W	0.98	1.00	0.97
Y	0.98	1.00	0.98

Figure 7 – Simulated test results [4].

As for the real tests, the results were close in relation to both the smartphone and the use of the Arduino Nano 33 BLE Sense. The answers were far from the previously proposed accuracy, only achieving results for the letters C, L, O and R, while the others

varied between total errors, that is, they gave different results for each test or a constant exchange between two or more letters. The difference between the two hardware occurred in the way the results were presented, being directly on the smartphone, shown in Fig. 8, and on the board, using the IDE's serial monitor, shown in Fig. 9, where the values represent the percentages. compatibility with each letter.

Figure 8 – Results on the smartphone [4].

Figure 9 – Results with the plate.

Accuracy errors when compared with simulation results for practice may have occurred due to factors such as lighting when collecting the image of the person making the sign in LIBRAS, the camera used and even the image quality used for training. . Therefore, to mitigate the errors found, and obtain better performance, some points can be made, such as: collecting the database closest to the real one, with several different lighting environments, testing neural network models with more neurons, among other characteristics of algorithm parameters. However, one of the project parameters must always be the characteristics of the hardware that is intended to be used in the product.

The proposed project and with the results already achieved and the proposals for improvements, it is possible to consider as positive the initiative to develop an image classifier within the field of accessibility and inclusion of the population with a future perspective of expanding communication to spoken, written and/or signaling.

Future development proposals include the use of hardware with greater processing capacity, while still maintaining low energy consumption, inclusion of gyroscope and video movement recognition for greater storage of training and testing data and thus making it

more accurate. the image classification system in expanding to a complete sentence translation system, providing greater comfort in communication between people with hearing impairments and those without such impairment, as an important factor of social inclusion.

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